

INDICATORS FOR ASSESSING URBAN CLIMATE CHANGE VULNERABILITY
AND RISK AT THE NEIGHBOURHOOD SCALE IN OTTAWA, CANADA

By

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This paper is accepted as conforming
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Abstract

Even if communities are equally exposed to climate hazards, such as flood, heat, heavy rainfall, and extreme weather events, depending on their sensitivities and adaptive capacities, some groups or communities are affected disproportionately. Moreover, cities are more likely to be affected by multiple climate and non-climate factors simultaneously, which, in combination with poor land use planning, further exacerbates vulnerability of economically and socially marginalized groups (IPCC, 2022). Indicator-based methods, often used in vulnerability assessments or spatial tools, are one approach to help identify those groups.

This research paper identified indicators that can be linked to climate hazards, exposure, and sensitivity to assess vulnerability to climate change at a local level in the City of Ottawa. A literature review was conducted to identify indicators and spatial tools that have been used internationally to assess vulnerability. The research also considered Ottawa's risks to climate change for a set of context-specific indicators. The final 47 indicators were selected from altogether 680 indicators from 16 sources, and consist of three sets of indicators, a core set of 15 standard indicators for easier comparison with other cities, a second set of 22 context-specific indicators, and a third set of 10 optional indicators consisting of more standard indicators.

The results demonstrated that there was a high correlation between the standard indicators most used; however, Ottawa's context-specific indicators were mostly not among them and lack of geospatial data at a local scale was identified as possible reason. The selected indicators can assist Ottawa in identifying vulnerable communities to assist mitigation, adaptation, and city planning and they can also serve practitioners from other cities as basis for their own sets of indicators to assess vulnerability in non-coastal cities.

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Indicators for assessing urban climate change vulnerability and risk at the neighbourhood scale in Ottawa, Canada

Climate change is a complex problem of pressing concern that has been recognized and discussed globally. In its latest report, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has warned about the increasing risk to people and infrastructures in cities and urban areas and revealed growing “observed human and economic losses” (Dodman et al., 2022, p. 909).

Climate change poses risks to cities not only through direct climate impacts, but also through interactions of changing urban areas, exposure, and vulnerability (Dodman et al., 2022). Current and future climate hazards are affected by the changing climate, while exposure and vulnerability are influenced by non-climatic factors such as adaptation measures and inequalities caused by socio-economic processes, for example “gender, class, race, ethnic origin, [and] age” (Arnwell et al., 2021; Dodman et al., 2022, p.909).

To help reduce impacts and risks of climate change to vulnerable groups, climate actions need to be targeted towards communities most at risk. Mitigation and adaptation measures can only be effective, if they recognize that some places, people, or groups face multiple disadvantages which increases their vulnerability disproportionately. Because vulnerability is a “relative measure”—which cannot be observed or measured (Downing et al., 2002, p. 3)—the use of indicators has been a common approach to predict vulnerability to climate impacts and to compare different socioeconomic groups (Barankin et al., 2021).

This research paper identifies indicators for assessing vulnerability of Ottawa’s communities. The indicators are a combination of most common/ standard indicators and indicators specific to Ottawa and will allow the identification of communities or populations at

greater risk at the neighbourhood scale. A comprehensive list of all indicators is provided in Appendix A and can be used as a basis for other non-coastal cities.

Research Context and Purpose

This research paper was the outcome of a placement at an organization in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Graduate Certificate in Science and Policy of Climate Change through Royal Roads University. It was an opportunity to not only contribute my knowledge and help the organization, but also to learn about applied climate solutions.

The idea for the research on indicators emerged when I learned from my colleague about his work with the City of Ottawa and their need for a spatial-based tool to identify Ottawa communities most at risk to top climate hazards (Stantec, personal communication, July 20, 2022).

This research attempts to shine a light on indicators that assess vulnerability, their merits, and shortcomings. Based on a literature review, I recommend indicators specifically for the needs of Ottawa, that could assist the city in identifying and understanding communities most at risk. This knowledge can help city officials to develop socially just climate actions that effectively reduce climate risks for vulnerable communities (McCarney, 2012).

The research could also assist decision making processes for city planning, e.g., land use, tree planting, transportation planning, community improvement plans, and operations, e.g., emergency response, and social service program priorities (Stantec, personal communication, July 20, 2022). And over time, socioeconomic monitoring can help measure progress and impacts of climate actions on reducing vulnerability and risk (Adger et al., 2018).

Research Question

Vulnerability varies across people and places, with some being more susceptible to climate change impacts than others. Based on Ottawa's needs and the objectives outlined in the placement proposal, I identified the following research question:

What are appropriate indicators to assess Ottawa's vulnerability to climate change at the neighbourhood scale?

Objectives

As outlined in the placement proposal, first, the initial review concentrated on literature and reports that discussed indicators, vulnerability and risk assessments using climate indicators, frameworks, and geospatial tools. The results helped identify indicators, to understand the process, and recognize limitations. The literature review also focused on available open-source geospatial data and literature on Ottawa to help find context-specific indicators.

Second, potential indicators of sensitivity, exposure, and adaptive capacity were identified, extracted from the literature, and compiled in one table. Domains were identified from the extracted indicators and a vulnerability framework was developed, which helped to assign the indicators, find, and remove duplicates, and to gather similar indicators into common new indicator groups. Then, criteria were identified for selecting appropriate indicators for Ottawa and the final selection was made.

Finally, geospatial data found in the first step, such as climate, infrastructure, and census data, was evaluated and gaps in data availability were noted. This last step helped to identify the need for future research, surveys, or workshops. The results are not without limitations, and a description of encountered problems and [limitations](#) was included.

Literature Review

Globally, climate change had physical and mental health impacts on people in many regions, including heat-, flood- and extreme weather-related compromised infrastructure, economic losses, services disruptions, health impacts and mortality (IPCC, 2022).

Cities were more likely to be affected by multiple climate and non-climate factors simultaneously, which, in combination with poor land use planning and “siloeed approaches to health, ecological and social planning” further exacerbated impacts and losses, and increased vulnerability, especially of economically and socially marginalized groups (IPCC, 2022, p. 32).

Many of those non-climatic factors and inequalities are caused by social processes such as “differences in wealth and capacity...gender and non-binary gender, education, health, political power and social capital... age, including young and elderly, low physical fitness, pre-existing disability, length of residence and social and ethnic marginalisation” (Dodman et al., 2022, p. 929).

Even if communities are equally exposed to climate hazards, some groups or communities are affected disproportionately, and vulnerability assessments can be used to identify those areas at higher risk (WSP, 2021). To assess climate vulnerability and risks of Ottawa’s communities, a better understanding was needed of how people are exposed to climate change impacts, what resources they have available to cope, and how they can be helped if they are vulnerable.

Definition of Terms

This research adopted the definitions from IPCC’s 2018 report, that describes *hazard* as a potential climate-related event or impact that may negatively affect health or fundamental facilities, systems, or services; *exposure* as “the presence . . . in places and settings that could be adversely affected” (p. 549), *vulnerability* as the tendency “to be adversely affected” (p. 560), *sensitivity* as the “susceptibility to harm” (p. 560); *risk* as the “potential for adverse consequences . . . [which result] from the interaction of vulnerability (of the affected system), its exposure over time (to the hazard), as well as the (climate-related) hazard and the likelihood of

its occurrence” (p. 557); and *adaptive capacity* as the ability to adjust and respond to damage and consequences (IPCC, 2018).

Use of Indicators

Climate change Vulnerability Assessments (VAs) have been a common approach by decision makers to help understand potential effects of climate change and monitor adaptation strategies (Hinkel, 2011). Because it is a “theoretical concept”, vulnerability is not measurable and thus should be made “operational”, which involves a “method (an operation) for mapping it to observable concepts . . . [and] indicators constitute one approach to making theoretical concepts operational.” (Hinkel, 2011, p. 200).

Indicators are often seen as way to link academic work and political needs and they may help to understand and combine complex concepts into simple numbers, for example, socio-economic indicators such as income of a system (e.g., a community) can help to predict their vulnerability to climate impacts (Hinkel, 2011).

Limitations and Challenges

Many scholars agree that indicator-based methods need to be improved because studies often did not validate “the relationship between social indicators and observed climate change-driven impact . . . using robust predictive statistical models” and even more studies used the “unjustified equal-weighting approach” (Barankin et al., 2021, p. 8; Hinkel, 2011). Hinkel (2011) further argued that indicators of vulnerability and adaptive capacity used in vulnerability assessments are only suitable for identifying “vulnerable people, regions or sectors . . . [at] local scales and when systems can be narrowly defined by few variables” (p. 204), and that they should always offer sufficient background information on how they were interpreted, and they need to be updated frequently.

Scholars also observed in their research on sustainability indicators an excessive number of indicators that formed an “indicator industry”, which was appropriately described as “zoo” (King et al., 2000; Pintér et al., 2005; Tanguay et al., 2010; as cited in Merino-Saum et al., 2020, p. 2), with lacking agreement, guidelines, or an “established set of city indicators” (McCarney, 2012, p. 31).

Other studies found that strong interconnectedness of indicators, lacking agreements in the literature on their roles, and the possibility of alternative interpretations of the analysis of socially vulnerable groups causes uncertainties, which makes their selection and interpretation contestable (Lindley et al., 2011, Kazmierczak et al., 2015). Moreover, often geospatial data is either not available at the neighbourhood scale (such as social networks) or “difficult to represent” (such as the availability of insurance) (Lindley et al., 2011, p. 11). More recently, the drastically growing number of indicators further complicate the selection of relevant and suitable indicators (Merino-Saum et al., 2020).

Another challenge is the appropriate number of indicators that should be selected. While many indicators ensure that fewer aspects of vulnerability are overlooked, they also contribute to the complexity and might reduce the understandability (Merino-Saum et al, 2020). Smaller indicator sets can be as comprehensive as larger ones, if the indicators are chosen thoroughly and coverage of all crucial categories is ensured (Merino-Saum et al, 2020).

Ottawa’s Geography

Ottawa, Canada’s capital, is situated in south-east Ontario, nearby the city of Montréal and the U.S. border. The city has a land area of 2,788 square kilometres with a population of 1,017,449 people and a population density of 365 people per square kilometre (Statistics Canada, 2021).

Ottawa’s 2020 Climate Projection Report projected that Ottawa would become warmer all year around and wetter in all seasons, except summer, with less snowfall and a shorter snow

season in winter. Changes in seasons, periods of extreme heat and rainfall (both in volume and intensity), and conditions favourable for extreme events such as freezing rain, tornadoes and wildfires were predicted to increase (Ottawa, 2020).

Ottawa’s Hazards and Vulnerable Population Types

The final selection of indicators contains context-specific indicators (*italicized in following sections*); therefore, preliminary communication with staff members of the City of Ottawa was considered together with the information found in literature. Important hazards and other stressors that were identified by the city officials are extreme heat, changing seasons, extreme weather, flooding (fluvial and urban/ overland), power outages, and socio-economic factors (Stantec, personal communication, July 20, 2022).

Of 150 potential climate impacts assessed in Ottawa’s recent Climate Vulnerability and Risk Assessment (CVRA), 40 priority risks were identified that would require immediate action for the above-mentioned hazards, as well as drought, humidity, increased volume and intensity of precipitation, and global climate change (Ottawa, 2022).

Ottawa (2022) identified as most vulnerable population types “households with limited financial resources” (e.g., *female-headed households*, persons living in *poverty*, and people without *air conditioning*), “individuals that spend a significant amount of time outdoors” (e.g., *children and youth*, *recreation enthusiasts*, and *transit users*), “outdoor workers” (e.g., *agricultural workers*), “individuals with health conditions or limited mobility” (e.g., *persons with disabilities* and/ or *chronic illnesses*, including *mental health conditions*, *single-pensioner households*, and persons with limited access to *social support systems*), “disadvantaged or marginalized populations” (e.g., *Indigenous Peoples*), and “individuals experiencing homelessness/ precariously housed populations” (e.g., persons living in *social housing*) (p. 27).

Some groups, such as *senior residents*, may experience more than one vulnerability simultaneously, such as *disabilities*, *gender*, *race inequalities*, and *living alone*, and a connection has been found between those circumstances and the health and well-being of seniors (United Way Centraide, 2017). In 2017, 33% of Ottawa’s seniors (*aged 65 years and older*) had “some type of disability” (United Way Centraide, 2017, p. 21) and by 2035, seniors are expected to account for over 22% of the population (Ottawa, 2022). Other groups that may face multiple vulnerabilities are *renters*. 42% of renters and 14% of homeowners paid over 30% of their gross household income on housing, leaving less money to cope with climate change or other burden (Ottawa, 2022).

Finally, it was noted that *rural communities*, including agricultural lands, make up 80% of the city’s land area and that they could be more vulnerable to climate change, due to “impacts to agricultural practices and livelihoods, water security for those on private wells, isolation during extreme events, and protection from vector-borne diseases” (Ottawa, 2022, p. 26)

Potential Impacts, Indicators, and their Relevance

The rationale for the selection of the indicators and their domains built upon previous research and studies discussed in 16 academic and non-academic studies and reports, and a summary with potential indicators (*italicized*), which have been selected among possible hazard-receptor combinations, is provided in this section. In addition, Sayers et al. (2017), provided a comprehensive justification of their indicator selection, based on extensive research and past experiences in Great Britain.

Recent immigrants and people who recently moved to the area may lack local knowledge (e.g., awareness of local flood risk) and social networks and people who have insufficient

English or French language knowledge are more likely to have difficulty to get help, understand guidance, or warnings (e.g., flood warnings) (Sayers, 2017).

Critical infrastructure (e.g., transportation, energy and water supply, and emergency services) is vulnerable to climate hazards. The spatial location, accessibility, drive time, and number of services (e.g., *public transit, fire stations, road density, and hospitals*) is critical because interruption of services could lead to “significant disturbances of social life and public safety as well as to negative cascade effects” (Schaefer et al., 2019, p. 13).

Extreme Heat, Heatwaves, and Droughts

Higher average *surface temperature* increases the occurrence of *heat island effects* (trapped heat due to densely packed buildings and *paved surfaces* with minimal *tree canopy*), increased water demand, increased energy demand (which may lead to brownouts or electricity outages), transportation disruption, and reduced quality of life (McCarney, 2012; Ottawa, 2022; Zhou et al., 2013; as cited in Tapia et al., 2017). While *green cover* reduces urban air temperature only slightly, it has a significant effect on day-time outdoor thermal comfort (Kleerekoper et al., 2017; Knight et al., 2021)

For physical infrastructure (e.g., buildings), mainly factors such *building age, composition, design* (Ottawa, 2022), and living standards (e.g., *building size and condition*) (Tapia et al., 2017) affect how it withstands extreme heat, for example, mechanical systems of older or poorly designed buildings may not be properly rated, and buildings may lack natural ventilation or *air conditioning* (Ottawa, 2022).

Scholars agreed that socio-economic factors, such as social isolation, very young age (McCarney, 2012; Tapia et al., 2017), “high age, chronic disease prevalence, [and] poverty” are key indicators for human vulnerability to heat stress, increased risk of health issues, and

mortality (Johnson et al. 2009; Laverdière et al. 2015; Reid et al. 2009; Sandholz et al. 2018; as cited in Birkmann et al., 2021, p. 5; McCarney, 2012).

In cities, heatwaves can cause “cramps, heat-exhaustion, and heatstroke, as well as are aggravated respiratory, cardiovascular, genitourinary and diabetes-related conditions” (Tapia et al., 2017, p. 4). During hot weather, increased hospital emergency admission rates were observed for heat-related illness in *children under five* (Climate Just, n.d.). *People 65 and older* had more heat related cardiovascular health issues and lower coping, and adaptive capacities (e.g., inflexibility to move to cooler areas), and people living in multi-family houses were lacking own gardens and depended on public *green spaces* (Birkmann et al., 2021).

Also, hotter summers may result in cancelled community services and events, reduced *outdoor recreation*, (EEA, 2012; Jacobset al., 2012; Schauser et al., 2010; as cited in Tapia et al., 2017; Ottawa, 2022) and the temporary closure of buildings without *air conditioning* (e.g., daycares, churches, *schools, kindergartens*), potentially increasing impacts to mental health and wellness, especially of people with *low income* that rely on these services and free events (Ottawa, 2022).

Both extreme heat and drought can lead to tree mortality, *effects on ecosystems* (Ottawa, 2022), and *ecosystem services*, causing food and water shortages, and increased food prices (McCarney, 2012). Moreover, higher *temperatures* with concurrent *reduced rain* result in earlier and weaker spring river flows, and lower water reserves later in summer (Montréal, 2017); however, impacts on urban water management systems are more difficult to identify because they are affected by many factors, such as water use, water stress, water quality, water infrastructure status, and *population density* (Stefano et al., 2015; as cited in Tapia et al. 2017).

Heavy Rainfall and Floods

Urban floods include river floods (fluvial), surface water floods (pluvial), and sewer floods. Pluvial flooding is caused by heavy or short duration high intensity (SDHI) rainfall that exceeds the carrying capacity of urban *drainage systems*, leading to “severe impacts on people and the economy” (Ottawa, 2022; Tapia et al. 2017, p. 4). For example, it may disrupt public services by damaging transportation and wastewater systems, and flood water may also enter buildings and damage them and their contents, potentially causing “health and safety concerns (e.g., from mold electrocution)” (Ottawa, 2022, p. 51). Moreover, due to its traumatic potential and possible schooling and home-life disruptions, flooding has been associated with “increased mental health and behavioural problems in *children* [emphasis added], such as aggressive behaviour and bed-wetting” (Climate Just, n.d., p. 1).

Flood risks are exacerbated in urban areas due to several factors, such as design, density, and age of *stormwater systems*, *elevation* (e.g., household floor levels), *slope* (e.g., slopes affect the direction of flood water and run-off can cause erosion on steeper slopes), *land use* (e.g., increased development and *imperviousness*), the ability to adapt, and existent early warning systems (Kazmierczak et al., 2015, Ottawa, 2022, Schaefer et al., 2019; Tapia et al., 2017). In urban areas unsealed or pervious surfaces are important because they allow the infiltration of heavy rain into subsoil (Schaefer et al., 2019).

To evaluate the health effects of green space and impervious areas in urban settings, the *normalized difference vegetation index* (NDVI) is often used to determine the differential reflection in the red and infrared (IR) bands which allows monitoring of density and intensity of green vegetation (Schaefer et al., 2019).

Extreme Weather Events and Power Outages

Ontario is “prone to extreme weather events like freezing rain and ice storms, extreme winds and gusts, and tornados” and resulted in catastrophic losses that “exceeded \$20 billion” since 2009 (Ottawa, 2022, p. 62). Extreme weather events, such as storms, can cause disruption of public water supply, increased risk of deaths, injuries, water and food-borne illnesses, post-traumatic stress disorders, cancelled *insurance* or increased premiums, loss of property, population migrations, and power outages (Lindley et al., 2011; McCarney, 2012; Ottawa, 2022).

Power outages or brownouts can result in compounding and cascading impacts, such as “overwhelming of emergency response and community support systems” during emergency situations (Ottawa, 2022, p. 30), effects on “life support equipment” (e.g., oxygen generators, ventilators), or effects on mobility of people “in electric wheelchairs requiring recharging and/or access to lifts” (Kazmierczak et al., 2015, p. 12).

Geospatial Data Availability

There was a notable amount of geospatial data available; however, some data was at a city scale (not at a neighbourhood-level) and all census data was based on dissemination areas (DA), the smallest standard geographic area used by Statistics Canada. Most indicators rely on census data, Open Data Ottawa, CANUE, Ottawa’s Neighbourhood Equity Index (NEI) and Ottawa Neighbourhood Study (ONS); other sources were geoOttawa, Ottawa Public Health, Open Street Map, and Google Earth.

Methods

This research paper combines a semi-systematic literature review as theoretical foundation to find and learn about indicators to assess vulnerability, and a qualitative data

analysis of all indicators compiled (secondary data) to identify the indicators most suitable for Ottawa. Figure 1 shows the research process used to find and identify the indicators.

Figure 1

Research Process for Identifying Indicators

Literature Review on Indicators

The aim of the literature review was to gain knowledge on indicators that assess vulnerability, on their use, merits, shortcomings, previous studies, and to learn climate related background information about the City of Ottawa, such as completed vulnerability and risk assessments, climate action plans, climate projection reports, and health reports. Relevant data sources were identified using search engines, such as Royal Roads University's library, Google

Scholar, and Google for 'grey literature'. Several procedures were followed to ensure a credible and reproducible review of literature. Credibility was ensured by including peer-reviewed data sources; however, findings from grey literature were included to draw information from technical and research reports, and governments.

Search Strategies

Multiple search terms and Boolean logic combinations were used for the search with three search engines, the RRU library, Google Scholar, and Google (Table 1).

Table 1

Search Terms and Boolean Logic Combinations Used for Literature Review

National and International Literature on Indicators and Ottawa		
Base search term		("climate" OR "climate change") AND "indicators" AND ("urban" OR "socio-economic indicators" OR "indicator-based")
Added search term options	1	AND ("vulnerability" OR "risk" OR "exposure" OR "adaptation" OR "mitigation") AND ("local scale" OR "locally" OR "local indicator")
	2	AND ("assessment" OR "Risk") AND ("spatial" OR "GIS" OR "tool" OR "geospatial" OR "mapping")

Procedure

The searches were conducted between August 5 and 17 and were restricted to sources published between 2010 and 2022 and in English language. First, titles and/or abstracts were

screened of the first 30 search returns for each of the searches. 104 articles, reports, and websites were identified as relevant and downloaded/ recorded for further evaluation (Table 2).

Second, sources were evaluated, and abstracts were screened to confirm they met study inclusion criteria for each specific search purpose. Inclusion criteria was met if the papers included indicators that assess vulnerability or related supporting information in urban context. Reference sections of the results were also searched, to find additional relevant sources. I also included papers which I reviewed for my master's research paper.

To minimize biased results, I ensured inclusion of studies opposing my opinion and to keep results from a wide range of cities, countries, and sources; however, I did focus on North America, Western Europe, and Asia due to some geographic, cultural, developmental, and economic similarities. Third, papers and information of the final selection were organized, documented, and findings were abstracted.

Table 2

Search Terms and Results of Sources Published between 2010 and 2022 (Searches Conducted August 5th to 17th, 2022)

Date of Search	Search Terms or Strategies Used	# of Hits/ Results	Notes	Selected Articles
RRU Library				
August 5-6	kf:(“climate” OR “climate change”) AND “indicators” AND (“urban” OR “socio-economic indicators” OR “indicator-based”) AND (eu:Peerreviewed) AND (yr:2010..2022)	5,703	Peer Reviewed and published in English language only. Reviewed first 30 best matches.	27
Google Scholar				

August 7	("climate" OR "climate change") AND "indicators" AND ("urban" OR "socio-economic indicators" OR "indicator-based")	30,200	Type: Review articles Reviewed first 30 results sorted by relevance.	20
Google				
August 9	("climate" OR "climate change") AND "indicators" AND ("urban" OR "socio-economic indicators" OR "indicator-based")	214,000,000	Reviewed first 30 results sorted by date or relevance.	11, 6 websites
August 9	("climate" OR "climate change") AND "indicators" AND ("urban" OR "socio-economic indicators" OR "indicator-based") AND ("vulnerability" OR "risk" OR "exposure" OR "adaptation" OR "mitigation") AND ("local scale" OR "locally" OR "local indicator")	8,190,000	Reviewed first 30 results sorted by date or relevance. Many results duplicated from previous search. Found additional 3 results through sources.	11
August 10	("climate" OR "climate change") AND "indicators" AND ("urban" OR "socio-economic indicators" OR "indicator-based") AND ("assessment" OR "Risk") AND ("spatial" OR "GIS" OR "tool" OR "geospatial" OR "mapping")	36,700,000	Reviewed first 30 results sorted by date or relevance. Many results duplicated from previous search.	9
Google or links provided by Ottawa				
August 12	- "edmonton" climate change "indicator" - "vancouver" health coastal flooding - United Way Seniors Vulnerability Index GIS tool "2019" - City Community Well	- 1,480,000 - 6,760,000 - 291,000 - 7,680,000	Used provided links or googled terms suggested by Ottawa. In Google, I chose the matches that were identical or closest to the provided terms of	10

	Being Plan "ottawa" spatial - "Older Adult Plan" AND "ottawa" AND spatial	- 914	the first 5 results sorted by date or relevance.	
August 17	- Ajax GIS-based climate risk analysis for emergencies, flood, nature/ trees, vulnerable buildings - Whitby GIS-based climate risk analysis for emergencies, flood, nature/ trees, vulnerable buildings	- 80,000 - 83,800	Used provided five links or two googled terms suggested by Dan. In Google, I chose the matches that were identical or closest to the provided terms of the first 5 results sorted by date or relevance. I also found one additional result in the sources.	10 (incl. websites)

Analysis of Suitable Indicators for Ottawa

Of the 104 articles and reports with information on climate change indicators, 33 were reviewed in depth and 1035 indicators (including duplicates) from 21 international articles and reports were extracted and compiled into one table. The sources were a mix of peer-reviewed literature and reports that used indicators for their vulnerability and risk assessments or mapping tools. Indicators were combined and duplicates removed, including indicators that were not applicable for Ottawa, i.e., sustainability or coastal indicators. The final selection of indicators was based on 680 indicators from 16 sources, and it consisted of 15 most common/ standard indicators (Category 1), 22 context-specific indicators (Category 3), and 10 more standard indicators (Category 2).

Procedure

All 1035 indicators were compiled in one table. Most indicators already contained information on the type of hazard (e.g., heat or flood) and dimension (e.g., exposure or

sensitivity). Three more fields were added to be able to categorize all indicators, spatial scale (e.g., national or neighbourhood), domain (e.g., age), and a new common indicators name ('Indicator Name'). Next, all indicators were assigned to a spatial scale and to one of 21 different domains (Table 3).

Table 3

Final 21 Domains with Examples of Corresponding Indicator and Statistical Summaries

Domain	Indicator Example	'Most Used' (Sum)	'Most Cited' (Sum)
Accessibility	Hospital, EMS station, GP, or health center - number, access, and distance	43	18
Age	Children < 5 years old	21	64
Atmospheric	Surface Temperature	14	16
Economic	Poverty rate	15	15
Ecosystem	Effects on Ecosystem Services	5	
Education	Education level	13	21
Geography/ topography	Green/ Blue Land Cover, impervious area	45	68
Health/ disability/ health care	Long-term illness or disability	24	14
Household composition	Female single-parent households	15	6
Housing cost/ house prices	Housing Costs of Renters	2	
Housing/ tenure/ air conditioning	Social renters	33	55
Income	Employment/ unemployment rate	48	42
Infrastructure/ utilities	Drainage network/ pipelines density/ condition of collection systems	3	12
Institutional/ governmental	Schools, kindergartens	16	31
Insurance	Risk Insurance availability	7	8
Local knowledge	Past experience	3	8
Minority and immigration status/ gender/ language	Racialized/ visual minority groups	43	24
Mobility	Public transit - use, distance, and access	1	
Occupation type	Outdoor workers	2	1

Population	Population density	8	35
Social networks	Social support/ social network	4	6
Grand Total		365	444

Next, missing data were added to all fields, and within each domain, all related indicators were grouped by assigning a new common indicator name. For example, children under 4 and under 5 were combined to ‘children under 5’. Figure 2 shows the analytical framework developed to assign domains, common indicator names, and all other data.

Figure 2

Analytical Framework Showing Links Between Potential Hazards, Exposure, Sensitivity, Adaptive Capacity, and the Assigned Domains

National, regional, and sustainability indicators were excluded. It was also noted how often each indicator was used (a) in this literature review ('Most Used'), and (b) in literature reviews done by two of the sources ('Most Cited'). This information was the base for ranking and selecting the category 1 and 2 indicators. To account for the high number of 'Most Cited' indicators, the 'Most Used' indicators found in this literature review were weighted with a factor of 2.5 (see [Discussion](#) section for details), then added to the sum of 'Most Cited' indicators and ranked, using the Excel data analysis tool for Rank and Percentile. The first 15 indicators were assigned to category 1, the next 10 indicators were assigned to category 2, and the 22 context-specific indicators of category 3 were based on this literature review.

Results

To identify suitable indicators to assess Ottawa's vulnerability to climate change at the neighbourhood-level, 104 articles and reports were screened, and 33 of them were reviewed in depth. Altogether, 1035 indicators (including duplicates) from 21 national and international articles and reports were extracted and compiled. The final indicator selection was based on 680 indicators from 16 sources (Table 4), and some of the indicators were additionally cited about 700 times in literature reviews conducted by two of the sources.

Table 4

Summary of 680 Indicators Collected from 16 International Articles and Reports (2010-2022)

Author(s)	Indicator Count	Indicator Type(s)	Hazard	Region	Sector/ Scale
Armenakis et al. (2017)	10	Socio-economic, demographic	Flood	Toronto	Urban
Bigi et al. (2021)	163	Exposure, sensitivity,	Flood	International	Urban

		adaptive capacity			
Bloomberg (2021)	12	Exposure, vulnerability	Climate, flood, heat	London	Urban
Climate Just (2018)	48	Sensitivity, enhanced exposure, ability to prepare, ability to respond, ability to recover	Flood, heat	Great Britain	Census Tract level
Jeganathan et al. (2021)	18	Sensitivity and adaptive capacity	Climate	Tamil Nadu, India	Natural, social, economic, infrastructure
Kazmierczak et al. (2015)	34	Sensitivity, enhanced exposure, adaptive capacity	Flood	Scotland	Agriculture, environment, and marine
Lindley et al. (2011)	89	Exposure, sensitivity, preparedness, response, recovery	Flood, heat	England	Census Tract level
Montréal (2017)	14	Social Susceptibility	Climate	Montréal	Urban
New Hampshire (2011)	16	Social Vulnerability	Climate	New Hampshire	Census Tract level
Rinner et al. (2013)	30	Sensitivity, exposure	Heat	Toronto	Urban
Sayers et al. (2017)	27	Susceptibility, ability to prepare, ability to respond, ability to	Flood	Great Britain	Census Tract level

		recover, community support			
Tapia (2017)	35	Sensitivity, adaptive capacity	Heatwaves, drought, flood	Europe	Human health, water planning, socio- economic tissue, and the urban fabric
USDN (2017)	39	Exposure, vulnerability	Climate	International	Urban
WSP (2021)	41	Vulnerability	Climate	Calgary	Urban
Yamamoto et al. (2021)	42	Sensitivity, exposure, adaptive capacity	Climate, air pollution	Edmonton	Urban
Yu et al. (2020)	62	Sensitivity, exposure, adaptive capacity	Climate, air pollution	Vancouver	Urban

The selection of indicators was based on the consideration of three factors, the literature review and how often they were used and cited in literature, the specific hazards Ottawa faces, and on available geospatial data. The latter factor was not an excluding factor, but rather to inform about the availability of spatial data and the potential need for future public involvement and further research to fill data gaps.

Based on the literature review, indicators for exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity were compiled and assigned to 21 domains (Table 3). The total number of final indicators was kept at 47 for the simplicity of information. While many indicators ensure that fewer aspects of

vulnerability are neglected, merely increasing the number of indicators does not guarantee comprehensiveness (Merino-Saum et al., 2020). Therefore, the final selection of indicators consisted of three sets, first, a core list of 15 standard indicators (Category 1) for comparison purposes, second, a set of 22 indicators (Category 3), that are “particularly pertinent for the urban area in question” (Merino-Saum et al., 2020, p. 16), and third, a set of 10 indicators (Category 2) with additional indicator options, consisting of the remaining most used and cited indicators for comprehensiveness. Indicators that initially belonged to category 2 were re-assigned to category 3 instead, if they were context-specific to Ottawa, to ensure they would be considered, even if the category 2 option was not chosen. Category 1 indicators may also contain Ottawa specific indicators. The final 47 indicators were used 365 times by the 16 sources and additionally cited 444 times (Table 5).

Table 5

Summary of 47 indicators for Ottawa including Potential Geospatial Data Sources

Indicator Name	Geospatial Data Source	‘Most Used’ (Sum)	‘Most Cited’ (Sum)
Category 1			
Building condition	Ottawa MPAC data (not public), census, ONS	7	18
Children < 5 years old	Census	11	24
Education level	Census, ONS, NEI	13	21
Employment/ unemployment rate	Census, CANUE, NEI, ONS	13	17
Flood characteristics/ flood risk	geoOttawa, Ottawa Flood Plain Mapping and Climate Change, RVCA Neighbourhood Flood Maps	9	26
Green/ Blue Land Cover, impervious area	Open Data Ottawa, geoOttawa, ONS, NEI, CANUE, NDVI	26	27
Hospital, EMS station, GP, or health center - number, access, and distance	ONS, NEI, geoOttawa, OpenStreetMap, Google Earth	41	21

Household floor level	Census, Ottawa GIS team data (developed for OPH)	10	20
Household income/ inequity	Census, NEI, ONS	35	25
Long-term illness or disability	NEI (diabetes, mental health), GeoOttawa (Long Term Care Homes), data unavailable for disability	18	14
People > 65 years old	Census, ONS	7	26
Population density	Census	6	33
Poverty rate	CANUE, NEI, ONS, census	8	4
Rainfall	CANUE, Open Data Ottawa (climate projections), weatherstats.ca	6	16
Recent immigrants/ immigrant status	Census	20	10
<hr/> Category 2 <hr/>			
Building size	Census	7	7
Economic recovery/ investments post disaster	geoOttawa (By-law 2017-295: Flood Plain Tax Deferral), Data unavailable	7	11
Elevation/ slope	HRDEM. Lidar / DEM Data by City of Ottawa	5	12
English or French Language Knowledge	Census	9	
Fire stations/ emergency rescue capacity, plans, and programs	Open Data Ottawa, ONS, Google Earth, OpenStreetMap	6	5
Insurance availability	Data unavailable	7	8
Land use	geoOttawa	6	9
Road density	Open Data Ottawa, geoOttawa, CANUE	6	8
Schools, kindergartens	ONS, NEI, OpenStreetMap, Google Earth	3	14
Single-parent households with dependent children	Census	9	4
<hr/> Category 3 <hr/>			
Activity status/ outdoor activities	CanALE provided by CANUE, Ottawa Neighbourhood Equity Index (NEI), Ottawa Neighbourhood Study (ONS)	3	
Air conditioning	Ottawa MPAC data (not public)	1	
Building age	Ottawa MPAC data (not public), ONS	3	10
Children of primary school age	Census	3	14
Chronic health problems/ multiple chronic conditions	Ottawa Neighbourhood Equity Index	1	

Drainage network/ pipelines density/ condition of collection systems	Water and Wastewater Infrastructure Map, geoOttawa	3	12
Effects on Ecosystems and Ecosystem Services	Data unavailable	5	
Female single-parent households	Census	1	
Females	Census	5	11
Heat island effect	NDVI, engage.ottawa.ca (heat island), OPH (Places to Cool Off Map)	1	
Housing Costs of Renters	Census, geoOttawa, NEI, ONS	2	
Indigenous status	Census, ONS	2	
Mental Health disease	NEI	2	
Outdoor workers	ONS	2	1
Public transit - use, distance, and access	CANUE, ONS, NEI, geoOttawa, OpenStreetMap	4	1
Racialized/ visual minority groups	Census, ONS	7	3
Rural area	geoOttawa	1	2
Rural population	Derived from Census and land use (geoOttawa)	2	2
Single-pensioner households	Census, NEI, ONS	5	2
Social renters	Census, ONS	5	
Social support/ social network	geoOttawa, NEI, ONS	4	6
Surface Temperature	CANUE, Open Data Ottawa (climate projections), weatherstats.ca	8	
Total		365	444

14 of the 16 sources (Table 6), i.e., academic literature, reports, and spatial tools, found that the three ‘most used’ indicators were first, number of, access to and distance to health care services (i.e., hospitals, EMS stations, general practitioners, or health centers), second, household income and inequity, third, green and blue land cover and impervious areas. The three ‘most cited’ indicators were based on extensive literature reviews done by the remaining two sources. The ‘most cited’ indicators were first, population density, second, green and blue land cover and impervious areas, and third, people aged 65 and older (Bigi et al., 2021; Tapia, 2017).

Table 6*Final 16 Literature Sources of the Selected Indicators*

Literature Source	Location	‘Most Used’ (Sum)	‘Most Cited’ (Sum)
Armenakis et al. (2017)	Toronto, Canada	7	
Bigi et al. (2021)	Urban (not coast)	82	415
Bloomberg (2021)	Greater London Area, England	9	
Climate Just (2018)	Great Britain	32	
Jeganathan et al. (2021)	Tamil Nadu, India	10	
Kazmierczak et al. (2015)	Scotland	20	
Lindley et al. (2011)	Great Britain	54	
Montréal (2017)	Montréal, Canada	6	
New Hampshire (2011)	New Hampshire, USA	11	
Rinner et al. (2013)	Toronto, Canada	21	
Sayers et al. (2017)	UK	14	
Tapia (2017)	European cities	13	29
USDN (2017)	Urban	15	
WSP (2021)	Calgary, Canada	20	
Yamamoto et al. (2021)	Edmonton, Canada	26	
Yu et al. (2020)	Vancouver, Canada	25	
Grand Total		365	444

Both types of sources (for ‘most used’ and ‘most cited’ indicators) appeared highly correlated (Figure 3), confirming that both source types independently came to similar conclusions regarding their choices of indicators (Figures 4 and 5). However, of the selected indicators specific to Ottawa’s needs (Category 3), most indicators (17 out of 22 category 2 and

3 indicators) were interestingly less frequently used indicators and even to a lesser extent cited by Bigi et al. (2021) and Tapia (2017).

Figure 3

Correlation Between 'Most Used' and 'Most Cited' Indicators

Figure 4

Chart Showing Relation Between 'Most Used' and 'Most Cited' Indicators (by Indicator)

Figure 5

Radar Chart Showing the Variation Between 'Most Used' and 'Most Cited' Indicators (by Domain)

Discussion

The results presented above yield a few implications for both research and practice, as well as limitations of findings. The literature review showed that there is an abundance of available indicators, but only a few guidelines and no established sets that may simplify the process for cities to assess vulnerability to climate change at the local scale.

The results of this research demonstrated that there was agreement on the common/standard indicators; however, the indicators selected specific for Ottawa were not much used or cited in the literature reviewed. In addition, many indicators were specific for coastal cities or developing countries, and they needed to be excluded. Moreover, the spatial scale and type of the

indicators had to be considered, for example, national or regional sustainability indicators are not useful for vulnerability assessments at the neighbourhood-level.

Also, while Ottawa-specific geospatial data was available for many indicators, for others, there was no or not sufficient data. Finally, another challenging consideration was the number of indicators, where practitioners might face two controversial issues, (a) too few indicators may lack comprehensiveness and (b) too many indicators may be too complex.

Consequently, existing indicator sets are a helpful basis, especially for comparing results of one city with another; however, this research highlights the importance to modify and expand existing sets to local characteristics for a context-specific indicator set.

Implications

First and foremost, the findings of this research could assist Ottawa in identifying and understanding communities most at risk, which can further help with the identification of just climate actions and city planning, and, over time, the evaluation of success of mitigation and adaptation strategies. Second, the selected indicators and geospatial data sources may also serve practitioners as basis when they build a set of indicators for other cities. A comprehensive list of all indicators and their definitions is provided in Appendix A and will allow other non-coastal cities to choose indicators specific to their needs.

While there was a high correlation between standard indicators collected during this research, Ottawa's context-specific indicators were mostly not among them. One possible reason could be the lack of geospatial data at a local scale. While there was comprehensive data for most indicators, others were lacking. For example, there was no public data on effects on ecosystems, numbers of people with disability, and availability of risk insurance (i.e., flood insurance). Several indicators were lacking wide-ranging spatial data, such as economic recovery

and post disaster investments, activity status and outdoor activities, outdoor workers, use of air conditioning, chronic health and multiple chronic conditions, mental health diseases, and social networks. Again, others were only at regional or city scale, such as rainfall and surface temperature. More research and data are needed to fill those gaps to be able to properly identify communities most at risk.

Considerations and Limitations

During the indicator extraction stage, several types for indicators were removed from the selection, i.e., sustainability indicators, coastal indicators, and indicators specific for the context of developing countries. Also, wildfire and smoke related indicators were excluded because they were not identified as a high probability currently or in the future in Ottawa's CVRA (Ottawa, 2022). Air quality, i.e., the likelihood of poor air quality (e.g., ozone, allergens), was identified as medium risk and therefore not considered for the selection of context-specific indicators at this time (Ottawa, 2022)

The selected indicators were based on two types of sources, (a) indicators 'most used' in reports, studies, spatial tools, and academic literature (14 sources), and (b) indicators 'most cited' in two of the sources that conducted exhaustive literature reviews of their own. One of the two sources, Bigi et al. (2021), provided a comprehensive list of indicators, which were cited 415 times; however, they were related to flood hazards only. When testing the results with and without the 'most cited' indicators, it was found that those indicators had a large effect on the outcome. Therefore, to account for the large number of 'most cited' flood indicators, the 'most used' indicators were weighted with a factor of 2.5.

Lastly, this research relies heavily (33% of the indicators) on large indicator sets developed in Great Britain by four sources between 2011 and 2017. To ensure the indicators did

not skew the results, results were tested and ranked without the UK indicators. Those test results showed still the same top indicators for categories 1 and 2, demonstrating that the UK indicators did not skew the results.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on a literature review, this research paper identified indicators that can be linked to climate hazards, (e.g., flood, heatwaves, extreme weather events), exposure, and dimensions of vulnerability, which may help explain why climate impacts are perceived differently in Ottawa's communities. Three sets of indicators were provided, a core list of 15 standard indicators for easier comparison with other cities, a second set of 22 context-specific indicators, and a third optional set of 10 indicators consisting of more standard indicators.

Altogether, 1035 indicators from 21 national and international articles and reports were extracted and compiled. The final indicator sets were extracted from 680 indicators and 16 sources. Existing indicator sets are a helpful basis; however, this research showed the importance to modify and expand existing sets to local characteristics, by removing indicators that do not apply, using indicators with common spatial scale and type, using indicators with available geospatial data, and providing sets of standard and context-specific indicators for comparability and comprehensiveness.

The results demonstrated that there was a high correlation between standard indicators collected during this research; however, Ottawa's context-specific indicators were mostly not among them and lack of geospatial data at a local scale was identified as possible reason.

A future scope to validate and implement the indicators, is (a) stakeholder consultation with staff members of the City of Ottawa, (b) creation of a framework to assess vulnerable communities, (c) testing and validating the indicators and framework on two communities, and

(d) implementation of the framework by the city. The validation process is a crucial step, as factors affecting vulnerability to climate change are strongly interconnected and identifying indicators with certainty is challenging (Kazmierczak et al., 2015).

The selected indicators can assist Ottawa in identifying vulnerable communities, which will not only help with mitigation, adaptation, and city planning, it can also help identify gaps in provided services and “improve public health planning, collaboration, and engaging individuals that need services” (New Hampshire Department of Health and Human Services, 2011, p. 1). In addition, the indicators and geospatial data sources may also be used by practitioners as basis for their own set of indicators to assess vulnerability in urban, non-coastal context.

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Appendix A